

Operational website and access facilities

Deliverable 1

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Objectives

The proposal set the objective of moving the static web pages of the IPCC Data Distribution Service (www.ipcc-data.org) to a server with greater than 99.9% availability. The dynamic pages will continue to be served from existing facilities with a lower level of guaranteed availability.

Approach

Selection of a hosting service

There are many web hosting services offering standard packages with the required level of availability. The quality of the services is monitored by a independent service inter-comparison sites.

A service was selected by selecting 3 hosting services which scored highly in two independent evaluations, and then examining the offers made by each in more detail. Cost and range of services were very similar in all cases (around £6 per month for a basic hosting package). The final decision was taken on the basis of the quality of the technical information made publicly available by the service provider.

The site is now hosted by Pickaweb (www.pickaweb.co.uk), a company created 1999 as one of the UK's first web hosting providers. Pickaweb has grown to host tens of thousands of websites. Company contact details are: Pickaweb Limited, Monomark House, 27 Old Gloucester Street. London, UK, WC1N 3AX, tel: 0800 802 1588, email: info@pickaweb.co.uk.

Issues resolved

The web pages have been moved into a github repository to streamline the maintenance of content, particularly the collaborative aspect of this work. The transfer to github highlighted some non-standard HTML in legacy pages which caused unreliable rendering of some pages. Systematic checking of pages against the W3C HTML validator has been used to track these errors and correct them. Following this work the majority of the pages comply with the full W3C schema. Minor errors remain in a range of legacy pages and will be cleaned up in the following 12 months.

In order to ease the maintenance of the site, the small collection of dynamic pages within the site have been moved onto a separate server under the new sub-domain apps.ipcc-data.org. The dynamic pages in question are:

- apps.ipcc-data.org/maps/: visualisation of climatologies;
- apps.ipcc-data.org/cgi-bin/down/: extracting files from archive;
- apps.ipcc-data.org/cgi-bin/down/_form/: constructing file request;

- apps.ipcc-data.org/cgi-bin/ddc_nav: selecting files and extracting spatial sub-sets.

In addition to the HTML pages, CEDA is also running an Apache forwarding service for the server at CIESIN, which is configured to ensure that calls to the URL <http://sedac.ipcc-data.org/ddc> get routed to the correct destination on the appropriate CIESIN server. The DNS record for the sedac.ipcc-data.org sub-domain is directed to the CEDA server, which then forwards the request to CIESIN. This configuration is in-efficient. CIESIN staff completed the re-configuration of their services in the last week of 2018. The DNS records managed by CEDA will be updated in the coming weeks to complete the change.

The migration of the site leads to a change in the maintenance work-flow. Changes can be drafted on the github pages. The final pages are migrated to the Pickaweb server using FTP. Other options which take advantage of the github continuous integration framework and the ability to synchronise the Pickaweb server directly with the github repository are also being evaluated.

Monitoring

The site is being monitored using an www.uptrends.com account (see figure 1), which checks the site availability every 5 minutes. Monitoring has been in place since 13th December 2018. In the first 20 days there was one negative result on 19th December at 5.23am. Tests are conducted every 5 minutes, so this implies 99.6% availability on the 19th, and 99.98% availability over the period as a whole.

Figure 1: site monitoring with UpTrends. The red bar in the top-right frame indicates a single failure of one of the site access tests which are conducted every 5 minutes.

